

THE USE OF NEGATIVE POLITENESS STRATEGIES IN A WORK OF ART (BASED ON THE ANALYSIS OF THE WORKS OF TAHIR MALIK)

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Abstract. *The article shows that there are four basic politeness strategies that can be summarized based on Brown and Levinson's theory, when and where to use one of these politeness strategies, negative politeness, based on the works of Tahir Malik analyzed.*

Keywords: *theory of politeness, pragmatics face - concept of face, positive face, negative face, sociopragmatics, negative politeness being conventionally indirect, questioning and hedging, be pessimistic, minimize the imposition, give deference strategies, S- speaker, H –hearer.*

Materials

In Uzbek linguistics S. Mominov, Sh. Iskanderova, M. Hakimov, Sh. Safarov and others studied the communicative, social and pragmatic aspects of speech, created textbooks and manuals. In particular, M. B. Kholova, who researched the theory of politeness, in the monograph "Linguocultural and sociopragmatic features of the category of politeness in English and Uzbek works of art" (2023), analyzed the categories of respect in the Uzbek language, where "negative politeness" strategies were analyzed. H. Komilova's dissertation entitled "Linguo-pragmatic study of speech etiquette units" contains considerable information about the principles of politeness in world linguistics and the methods of its manifestation in speech. Researching the theory and strategies of politeness in the Uzbek language from a sociopragmatic perspective is one of the most important tasks for linguists.

Methods

Brown and Levinson's politeness theory combines speech act theory and Grice's theory of implicatures with Goffman's notion of face, defined as "the positive social value a person effectively claims for himself by the line others assume he has taken during a particular contact" [1, 11] In fact, a face is nothing more than a self-image and the respect people have for each other. Showing awareness of someone's face can be socially close or distant. When talking to someone who is socially distant, such as a stranger, this concept implies respect or esteem, while talking to a socially intimate person, such as a friend, implies friendship or togetherness. Each participant in the interaction expects the other to respect his face. If not, a face-threatening action (FTA) is performed. To avoid this threat, it can be mitigated by using mitigations such as "please" or "maybe". This is called the Face Savings Act (FSA). Speakers usually do not intend to threaten someone else's face, and therefore "there are many ways to perform face-maintaining actions. The actions by means of which people cooperate in maintaining face are called "face-work". [2, 8] This set of methods is called the principle of politeness, and the strategies are socially manifested in different ways in communication. They must identify the pragmatic conditions on greetings and requests, for instance, according to the status, age, and sex of their co-participants. And they need to learn what the costs and benefits are of gaining (or losing) face in relation to others (Brown and Levinson 1987) [3, 574]

Introduction.

Politeness and pragmatics are the main concepts and objects of sociopragmatics. Courtesy (Politeness): It expresses the respectful attitude of interlocutors to each other in communication as mutual understanding and agreement. Politeness includes various social manners and behaviors that occur in the process of communication. Sociopragmatics studies the social role of language and how it shapes politeness in communication by analyzing these behaviors. Pragmatics is a branch of linguistics that deals with the use of language in social contexts and the clarification of the meanings of communication. Pragmatics is the study of how language units are used in context and how they affect listeners, which includes analyzes ranging from conversational maxims (Grice's Maxims) to implications (implicatures). Sociopragmatics, on the other hand, combines the analyzes of politeness and pragmatics to study how linguistics responds to social purposes and situations. Sociopragmatics analyzes how factors such as the social status of interlocutors, gender equality, cultural differences affect linguistic behavior and what role they play in interaction. Indeed, one of the main purposes of sociopragmatics ...is to find out how different societies operate maxims in different ways, for example by giving politeness a higher rating than cooperation in certain situations, or by giving precedence to one maxim of the Politeness Principle rather than another.[4 , 83] Politeness and pragmatics are an important part of sociopragmatics, and this field helps to understand the complexities of effective and social communication between listeners.

Results and discussion

Negative politeness strategy is realized by questioning and hedging, minimizing the imposition, apologizing, and stating the face threatening act as a general rule and, negative politeness strategy is applied when the rank of imposition is high and the participants have a big difference in terms of social distance and relative power. [5, 1] Negative politeness is redressive action addressed to the addressee's negative face: his want to have his freedom of action unhindered and his attention unimpeded. It is the heart of respect behavior; just as positive politeness is the kernel of "familiar" and "joking" behavior. [6, 129] Negative politeness is essentially based on avoiding or minimizing an imposition, or redressing the imposition, with apologies, deference, various kinds of hedges, impersonalizing, and other devices. [7, 45]

Strategy I: Being Conventionally Indirect. "Be traditionally indirect" means that the speaker chooses a way to communicate with the interlocutor not directly, but to some extent indirectly. This method is used in order to respect the interlocutor's independence and not to invade his personal space. In the process of speech communication, the form and content, the expressed thought and the thought to be expressed cannot be mutually symmetrical. One speech act can be aimed at different internal goals in different speech situations. This indirectly creates a speech act. [8, 117] So. This strategy is formed through indirect speech acts. Example:

The deputy held the phone to his ear and said,

"Yes, here," he looked at Zahid meaningfully. Then he handed over the phone:

- They are asking you? (1)

Astonished, the hermit put the receiver to his ear and said:

I hear, Sharipov," he said.

- What are you doing there? Who gave you the right to disrespect respectable people?

"I'm sorry, I don't know you?" Zahid said. (2)

When the head of the department introduced himself, Zahid said, "You are great!" he looked at Muovin in the sense that:

"I came here because of the ongoing case," he explained. [11, 56]

In case 1, the social relationship between the characters is asymmetrical, and the speaker uses the second person plural pronoun in relation to the listener, which creates politeness between them.

In the 2nd case, the modal word "sorry" is used to avoid conflict and one of the interlocutors softens the dialogue when the characters collide with each other.

Indirect speech is traditionally seen as a strategy to respect the listener's personal boundaries and maintain independence by establishing a secondary meaning or connotation that includes communication elements such as criticism, suggestions, or recommendations.

Strategy II: Questioning and Hedging. The use of hedge by a speaker can save the hearer's negative face since by putting a hedge the strength of an utterance will be modified. [5, 20] An example of this strategy can be seen in this expression:

- *"You don't know where he is now?"*

- *Where would he be, is he going to the grave, right here. Sister's deputy is now. Nomi's deputy, in fact, left all the work in her hands. Everyone is fed up with this devil's bitch.*

- *From what you say, you seem to hate him?* [11, 32]

Many speech acts contain the speaker's opinions and assumptions. Some of these are potentially FTAs, particularly assumptions about the hearer's beliefs, wants, and abilities. So as not to impose his views on the hearer, the speaker may qualify his statements, either as (1) to their veracity or (2) to the degree of the speaker's commitment to the view. [7, 50] This strategy asks the interlocutor something and leaves the opportunity to answer to his own discretion, instead of forcing him, he ensures his freedom. The speaker respects the listener's opinion and choice, and the interlocutor can answer this request at his own discretion.

In the hedging strategy, instead of saying something clearly, the speaker tries to express his opinion more softly and uses modal units like maybe, I think maybe:

- *"I didn't even think of that, don't worry." Maybe you can invite the Tulkin (name)?*

- *"The Tulkin (name)?" What does he have to do with this?*

- *In any case, he is a writer. Scholars can properly analyze the data they recover.* [12, 5]

This adds a certain freedom to the speaker's speech, prevents it from being perceived as a harsh statement, and respects the interlocutor's independence.

Therefore, these two strategies are used in communication to ensure that the interlocutors are careful about their personal boundaries and that they are not pressured. These methods of negative politeness help to make communication more respectful and polite, while avoiding disagreements or awkward situations between interlocutors.

Strategy III: Be pessimistic. This strategy gives redress to H's negative face explicitly expressing doubt that the conditions for the appropriateness of S's speech act obtain. [6, 173] This strategy is based on reducing the probability of the interlocutor's consent and maintaining the right to refuse. Using this strategy, the speaker anticipates that he will receive a negative response to his request or request, and therefore formulates his sentence accordingly:

- *"What if he has to?"*

- *"Are you telling the truth?" - said Tulkin, not hiding his surprise. But he added without waiting for an answer.*

- *"Then...if I need it for the experiment..."*

- *I just thought that you could help me logically sum up the experience, considering that you are a writer. If you feel like it, you can accept the offer.*

- *In that case, accept me only as an observer and commenting reporter.* [12, 6] The above communication aims to respect the interlocutor's freedom and keep the interaction smooth and respectful, while also showing the speaker's intention to use as little pressure as possible. This strategy of negative politeness allows you to continue the conversation without making the interlocutors feel uncomfortable.

Strategy IV: Minimize the imposition. This strategy uses units through expressions such as "it is not that important", "it won't take much time" [9, 33], and in order to reduce his need, the speaker makes his request or request polite and less important. by pretending to make the interviewer feel less forced. For example:

As soon as he took a step inside, the deputy got up angrily:

- "I'm busy!" I said?!

- "I heard," said Zahid. "Unfortunately, I'm running out of time, I can't wait any longer."

- I also have a lot of time. I can't accept you.

- *Even if you don't have time, I have to break in." This is my service.*

- Saying this, Zahid approached him and handed over his document. When the deputy got acquainted with the certificate, he was shocked.

With this tactic, the speaker seeks to control the interlocutor's personal time and space and maintain mutual respect. That way, communication stays healthy and constructive.

Strategy V: Give deference. The term deference was reserved by Brown and Levinson for a specific kind of negative politeness strategy (Strategy 5: Give deference). According to Brown and Levinson, deference involves conveying that the hearer is a higher social status than the speaker, either by the speaker humbling and abasing him, herself, or raising up the hearer. [10, 273] This strategy aims to respect the interlocutor's personal boundaries and independence by respecting his or her social status. This strategy recognizes the interlocutor's reputation, career, and personal space, and avoids direct or domineering behavior toward them.

Ways to implement the "Give deference" strategy:

- respectful address: the speaker addresses the interlocutor in a way that recognizes his status, for example, uses titles such as "Doctor", "Professor" or "Mr./Sir":

... *Manzura said "I cannot answer this question" to Dr. Khudoyor, looking for salvation*
Looked.

- *Leave the restaurant, sir. There is a lot of dirt there. A family building that will be built with good intentions let's not put its foundation on dirty ground.* [11, 68]

- caution in handling: the speaker handles in order to appreciate and show the thoughts and experiences of the interlocutor.

Conclusion. The main purpose of using negative politeness is to respect your interlocutor's personal freedom and boundaries. It is used to maintain the "social face" of the interlocutor by not disturbing him or intruding too much into his personal space. Negative politeness supports your interlocutor's sense of freedom and gives him a choice.

So, by using negative politeness strategies, you can maintain respect in communication with your interlocutor, avoid inconveniences, improve relationships, respect personal freedom,

keep communication sincere, and maintain respect criteria. This helps to make communication more effective and pleasant as opposed to contentious or chaotic.

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